

Title: High prevalence of low birth weight babies born to pregnant women referred to a district hospital in rural Zambia

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Abstract

Objectives: Low birthweight (LBW) is a significant public health problem in sub-Saharan Africa and LBW in rural Zambia is high. Our study explored the prevalence of LBW for newborns whose mothers were referred from a rural health center to a district referral hospital in Lundazi, Zambia.

Methods: A five-month retrospective record review of Ministry of Health data was performed to examine birthweight characteristics of a convenience sample of newborns from ten facilities referring to one district hospital ($n=234$).

Results: Among all cases, 21% ($n = 49$) of newborns were LBW. For LBW newborns, 73% ($n = 36$) were preterm with mothers having a pregnancy duration of less than 37 weeks. Newborns whose mothers experienced twin pregnancies ($p = .021$) and prolonged labor ($p = .033$) were more often LBW. However, regression models demonstrated no difference among newborns with and without LBW for prolonged labor ($p = .344$) and twin pregnancies ($p = .324$) when controlling for variables that could interact with the maternal-newborn delivery outcomes.

Conclusions for Practice: Healthcare providers and policy makers need to address the short and long-term effects of LBW throughout the lifecycle in rural Zambia. More maternal-newborn health research is needed to understand the underlying socioeconomic, social, and cultural determinants influencing LBW in rural Zambia.

Objectives

Low birthweight (LBW) is a significant public health problem in sub-Saharan Africa where 14% of newborns are born weighing less than 2500 g each year (AFRO WHO, 2019). The World Health Assembly endorsed a *Comprehensive Implementation Plan on Maternal, Infant*

and Young Child Nutrition in 2012 that included the goal to achieve a 30% reduction in the number of infants born with a weight lower than 2500 g by the year 2025 (WHO, 2014). The *Global Nutrition Targets 2025* align with the *Global Strategy (2016-2030)* roadmap to achieve right to the highest attainable standard of health for all women, children and adolescents –to transform the future and ensure every newborn, mother and child not only survives, but thrives (WHO, 2015). In Zambia, the overall percentage of LBW in Zambia dropped from 13.5% in 2000 to 11.6% in 2015 (WHO, 2019). Our study, set in the context of the *Global Nutrition Targets 2025* and *Global Strategy (2016-2030)*, explored the prevalence of LBW for newborns whose mothers were referred from a rural health center to a district referral hospital in Lundazi, Zambia.

Methods

A five-month retrospective record review of Ministry of Health data was performed to examine birthweight characteristics of a convenience sample of newborns from ten facilities referring to one district hospital ($n=234$) in the Eastern Province of Zambia. There were no missing data in records reviewed for gestational age and birthweight.

Prior to beginning the study, Institutional Review Board approval was obtained from the XXX (XXX) and XXX (XXX), and the XXX in Zambia was informed. Permission for data collection was obtained from the Hospital Administrator and District Health Officer directly responsible for oversight of the facility in Zambia.

Results

Among all cases, 21% ($n = 49$) of newborns were LBW. For LBW newborns, 73% ($n = 36$) were preterm with mothers having a pregnancy duration of less than 37 weeks. There were

no significant differences for LBW newborns and demographic characteristics or labor complications (Table 1).

Newborns whose mothers experienced twin pregnancies ($p = .021$) and prolonged labor ($p = .033$) were more often LBW. However, regression models demonstrated no difference among newborns with and without LBW for prolonged labor ($p = .344$) and twin pregnancies ($p = .324$) when controlling for variables that could interact with the maternal-newborn delivery outcomes.

Conclusions for Practice

There are multiple causes of LBW, including early induction of labor or caesarean birth (for medical or non-medical reasons), multiple pregnancies, infections and chronic conditions such as diabetes and high blood pressure (WHO, 2014). While research on the causes of LBW in rural Zambia is limited, in urban Zambia researchers conducted a large retrospective cohort analysis and found a LBW prevalence of 10.5% with placental abruption, delivery before 37 weeks, and twin pregnancy being associated with LBW in multivariable analysis (Chibwesa et al., 2016). Poor nutrition in the womb increases the risk of death and if newborns survive they tend to have impaired immune function and increased risk of disease. Moreover, they are likely to remain undernourished, with reduced muscle strength, cognitive abilities and IQ throughout their lives (UNICEF, 2019). Additionally, preterm neonates who survive are at greater risk of short- and long-term morbidities (Chawanpaiboon et al. 2019).

Affordable, accessible and appropriate health care is critical for preventing and treating LBW (WHO, 2014). Evidence-based interventions to prevent LBW can be introduced in health-care and nutrition services, using the maternal and perinatal platforms, and focused on universal routine antenatal care with fetal and infant-child growth monitoring (WHO, 2014). Evidence-

based interventions to prevent LBW recommended by the WHO (2014) include: support for women's empowerment and educational attainment, community-based packages of care to improve linkage and referral for facility births, adequate birth spacing, fetal growth monitoring at all levels of care, and balanced protein-energy supplementation. All programs should be cognizant of the beliefs and preferences of women with respect to their health, the unbalanced gender relations and power distribution between women and men, and the inequalities between groups of women with respect to race, ethnicity and residential segregation (WHO, 2014).

This study has several limitations. Data regarding the reason for referral to the district hospital was not recorded in the delivery register, therefore we are unable to report details on obstetric morbidity. Additionally, information on the proportion of high risk pregnant women in the district referred to the referral hospital is not known, therefore we cannot provide specifics about what fraction of the population is born with LBW nor make comparisons to the average birthweight of babies in Lundazi. Researchers in the neighboring district conducted a cross sectional descriptive study and found that complications resulting in hospital referral most commonly included post-partum hemorrhage (70%), prolonged labor (70%), malpresentation (50%), antepartum hemorrhage (40%), and retained placenta (40%) (Benson, Benson, & Luke, 2019). Results of our study did reveal high LBW births in one region of Zambia, although the data are not generalizable to other regions in Zambia, and more in-depth data regarding antenatal care were not available.

There is a clear need to improve estimating gestational age in this population. Gestational age is one of the most important features of a pregnancy when making clinical decisions, especially for the management of delivery, such as the timing of a caesarean section before labor or when to induce labor (Smith & Nakimuli, 2020). Accurate estimation of gestational age is

needed to optimize delivery location for preterm births and is a prerequisite to identify and manage fetal growth abnormalities (Deb et al., 2020). Ultrasound dating in early pregnancy is the most accurate method to assess gestational age but less available in LMICs (Lee et al., 2017). Where ultrasound is not possible, such as many regions of rural Zambia, increased efforts are needed to develop simpler yet specific approaches for newborn assessment through new combinations of existing parameters, new signs, or technology (Lee et al., 2017).

Additional focus must be paid to educating women about the importance of adequate nutrition in pregnancy. Healthcare providers and policy makers need to take steps to address the effects of LBW throughout the lifecycle in rural Zambia. This will undoubtedly require a multidisciplinary and multisectoral approach. Affordable, accessible and culturally appropriate health care is critical for preventing and treating LBW (WHO, 2015). More global health research is needed to understand the underlying socioeconomic, social, and cultural determinants influencing LBW in rural Zambia.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Table 1 Birth weight characteristics of newborns after delivery at district referral hospital

Maternal-Newborn Health Indicator	Total (n = 234)	Birth weight		Statistical Tests	
		≤ 2500 g (n = 49)	> 2500 g (n = 185)	Pearson Chi-Square	Adjusted P value
Referral facility	% (n)	% (n)	% (n)		(2-sided)
MWH	60.7% (142)	61.2% 30	60.5% 112	.008	.931
Non-MWH	39.3% (92)	38.8% 19	39.5% 73		
Missing	none				
Distance					
≤ 12 km	35.5% (83)	49% (24)	33.5% (62)	5.339	.069
> 12 km	64.1% (150)	51% (25)	65.9% (122)		
Missing	0.4% (1)	none	0.5% (1)		
Age group					
15 to 19	39.7% (93)	3.3% (16)	41.6% (77)	2.591	.628
20 to 24	29.1% (68)	30.6% (15)	28.6% (53)		
25 to 29	12.0% (28)	10.2% (5)	12.4% (23)		
30 to 34	8.1% (19)	10.2% (5)	7.6% (14)		
35 and older	9.8% (23)	14.3% (7)	8.6% (16)		
Mean (SD)	22.9 (6.9)	23.9 (8)	22.9 (6.5)		
Missing	1.3% (3)	2% (1)	1.1% (2)		
Gravida					
1	46.6% (109)	44.9% (22)	47% (87)	.111	.946
2-5	41.9% (98)	40.8% (20)	42.1% (78)		
6 and above	11.1% (26)	12.2% (6)	10.8% (20)		
Mean (SD)	2.6 (2.1)	1.7 (0.7)	1.6 (0.7)		
Missing	0.4% (1)	2% (1)	none		
Parity					
0	47.0% (110)	46.9% (23)	47% (87)	4.372	.112
1-5	48.3% (113)	42.9% (21)	49.7% (92)		
6 and above	4.7% (11)	10.2% (5)	3.2% (6)		
Mean (SD)	1.5 (1.9)	0.6 (0.6)	0.6 (0.6)		
Missing	none				
Duration of pregnancy (in weeks)					
< 28	0.4% (1)	2% (1)	none	9.432	.251
28 to <32	none				
32 to <37	73.5% (172)	71.4% (35)	74.1% (137)		
37 to 42	25.6% (60)	15.3% (13)	25.4% (47)		
<42	0.4% (1)	none	0.5% (1)		
Mean (SD)	36.5 (1.5)	36.2 (2.1)	36.6 (1.3)		
Missing	none				
Condition of baby					
Alive	94.4% (221)	% (46)	% (175)	.038	.846
Dead	5.6% (13)	% (3)	% (10)		
Missing	none				
Apgar score at 5 minutes					
0-6	15.4% (36)	12.2% (6)	16.2% (30)	.469	.493
7-10	84.6% (198)	87.8% (43)	83.8% (155)		
Mean (SD)	7.8 (2.4)	8.1 (2.4)	7.8 (2.4)		
Missing	none				
Breastfed within 1 hour					
Yes	81.2% (190)	14.3% (7)	20% (37)	.829	.418
No	18.8% (44)	85.7% (42)	80% (148)		
Missing	none				